

Daniel Formo

The Orchestra of Speech, a performance and installation

Performance

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

Performance and installation proposal: “The Orchestra of Speech”

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The Orchestra of Speech

“The Orchestra of Speech is a part sound installation, part instrument and performance concept coming out of a recent artistic research project exploring the relationship between music and speech, particularly that of improvised music and everyday conversation. Not *what* we are saying, but *how* we say it – how the intonation, register, tempo, rhythm, dynamics, and voice quality form a communicative layer of its own in speech. These features have pragmatic functions in speech for signaling turn taking, highlighting important information and for interpreting intention, but from a musical point of view it is also interesting to see how these structures also can make recognizable and meaningful patterns in music.

In both music and speech, we tend to make use of different *genres* as formal frameworks when constructing utterances. In speech, these genres include choice of words, but also musical traits like certain registers, dynamic ranges, tempi etc., that taken together forms a musical character that communicates something about the social situation and relation and thus give a context for interpreting intentions: *small talk, pillow talk, baby talk, interrogation, public address, report, confession*, etc. are examples of speech genres where the form is part of the meaning. A musical exploration of such genres is one of the main themes in this project.

In order to do this in practice I have developed a metaphorical “orchestra”, an *instrument-like* system for analyzing, abstracting and orchestrating musical features from speech in real time. Collections of different speech recordings are analyzed, processed and played back through this system. This instrument can be used both as an extended instrument, as well as an interactive sound installation reacting to input from audiences

When used as an instrument, the system can analyse input from speech or piano, and when presented as an installation, an analog telephone set connected to the system rings from time to time, inviting members of the audience to pick up the phone and interact with the orchestra by speaking to it. The system analyzes the input and uses machine learning to respond with semantically nonsensical but musically probable responses, thus allowing a kind of meta-dialogue between speech and music.

Another theme explored in this project is *sound*, and how sound source and sound quality affects the perception and meaning of sound. The software instrument system is connected to a setup of transducers attached to acoustic instruments, resulting in a physical electroacoustic orchestra that blurs the line between electric and acoustic, voice and instrument, and between virtual and real. The sound of an acoustic instrument somehow *means* music, and creates a frame of reference that invites musical listening, while a voice mediated through a loudspeaker have connotations of broadcast and public address. The invisible sound wall of stereo loudspeakers creates virtual sonic spaces. New perspectives for listening appear when these sonic realms start to blend in an orchestration of different sound qualities and physicalities.

The theme of perception is another focus in this project – how far can speech be abstracted musically before the communicative features are lost? Does the listening focus always switch between semantic and poetic/musical meaning, or is it possible to perceive both the same time? On a more general level it can also be considered an exploration of meaning in music, and the many ways music and speech can make sense.